

Studies in the Coagulations of Colloids. Part XV. New Aspects of Gold Sol Coagulation.

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In respect of the kinetic studies of its coagulation, the wide variety of the methods and conditions of its preparation, the correlation of some of the chief physical constants, especially optical properties, with the size and shape of the particles etc., the gold hydrosol is amongst the most well investigated of colloid systems, since practically the beginning of the growth of the subject at the hands of a number of well known workers. It *most nearly* fulfils the requirements of a monodisperse sol. The positions, the intensities of its characteristic absorption bands, and especially the marked variations in them during coagulation have especially favoured the selection of the gold sol for accumulating data in relation to the predictions of the theories for the kinetics of coagulation and allied changes, as developed especially by Smoluchowski (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1917, **92**, 129) and Freundlich ("Colloid and Capillary Chemistry," 1926, pp. 442-450) and others.

This has produced a mass of experimental results which have in the main confirmed the requirements of the theory in the region of *rapid* coagulation. Previous papers in this series (Joshi and co-workers, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 329, 599; 1934, **11**, 133, 555, 573, 797; 1936, **13**, 141, 217, 309, 311, 439; *J. chim. phys.*, 1935, **32**, 455; *Proc. Acad. Sci. U. P.*, 1935, **5**, 41; *Bombay Univ. Journ.*, 1935, **4**, 140; *Kolloid Z.*, 1936, **76**, 145; *Current Science*, 1936, **4**, 481, 870) on the *slow* coagulations of a number of sols and dilute emulsions (which were presumably *polydisperse*.) have shown, however, that departures from the theory, arise chiefly because Smoluchowski (*loc. cit.*) has assumed tacitly that even in the *slow* region, coagulation is but a *time continuous* coalescence of the primaries. It was of interest therefore, to examine the behaviour of the gold sol from the standpoint of this deduction in regard to the deficiency in the current theories. It will be seen that the results now reported confirm the criticism developed in this series.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The gold sol was prepared according to a method due to Zsigmondy (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1906, **12**, 721). 10 C. c. of 0.38% gold chloride solution were added to 200 c. c. of twice distilled water and made alkaline by means of 10 c. c. of 0.2 *N*-potassium carbonate solution. The solution was then heated to the boiling point and 5 to 6 c. c. of 0.3% formalin were added drop by drop with continuous shaking. A fine, transparent red sol was obtained, which was boiled for a short time. Only Jena vessels were used during this work. The sol was next dialysed against repeated changes of redistilled water, till the dialysate was free from the chloride. The course of the coagulation was studied by observation of the corresponding change of the viscosity and of refractive index. The course of the sol during coagulation, relative to that of water was measured by Scarpa's method with modifications described previously (Joshi and Viswanath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 329). The suction applied was kept constant at 29.35 + 0.05 cm. of water. The observation of the water level being made with a low power telescope. The temperature of the thermostat was 80 + 0.05°. Equal volumes of the sol (10 c. c.) and of coagulating solution, which had already attained the thermostat temperature were mixed in the Scarpa tube at a known time and the viscosity of the mixture measured at suitable intervals till visible flocculation set in. The concentration of the coagulant is expressed in term of millimols (m. m.) of the electrolyte used in the coagulating mixture. The general procedure and precautions taken are described in an earlier paper (Joshi and Viswanath, *loc. cit.*). Of the colloids studied previously (*loc. cit.*) the viscosity of the gold sol approached most nearly that of water. Further more, the viscosity variations consequent on coagulation with dilute coagulants were small. These have not been shown in Fig. 1.

Thus refractive index for the D line was measured during coagulation by means of a Pulfrich refractometer as described previously (Joshi and Jaya Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 141). The results have been shown graphically in Figs. 1 and 2. They are but a few typical curves selected from a much greater number of viscosity—time and refractive index—time curves distinctive of numerous coagulations actually examined.

DISCUSSION.

The general indication of the viscosity—time curves in Fig. 1 con-

firmly the conclusion drawn previously from independent data accumulated in these laboratories, *viz.*

(a) Contrary to the tacit assumptions in general made by colloid chemists a coagulation does not always produce a net *rise* in the viscosity of the coagulating mixture. For example, in the coagulation represented by Fig. 1, curve 1, flocculation had set in immediately on the addition of the electrolytes; the corresponding viscosity however, shows an overall decrease.

FIG. 1.

(b) One of the early stages in a coagulation is usually though not invariably characterised by a diminution of viscosity, followed by a subsequent rise.

(c) The progress of the viscosity change during especially a *slow* coagulation is discontinuous with respect to the time of coagulation (Joshi and co-workers, *loc. cit.*). Gallecki (*Kolloid Z.*, 1925, **36**, 154 *et. seq.*) in the course of a comprehensive study of the physicochemical properties of the gold hydrosol, has observed the occurrence of minima on the viscosity—time curves in numerous coagulations. Whilst our results are in agreement with this, we are of the opinion that these minima are but a part of a wider continuous but *slow* coagulation, *viz.*, it is not time continuous but, *zonal, i.e.*, proceeds through a series of stages corresponding to the breaks or discontinuities on the coagulation—time curves. Gallecki (*loc. cit.*) has made interesting observations of conditions for the characteristic colour change, red to blue, and the corresponding viscosities. As has also been found that due to prolonged 'ageing' the viscosity falls to a minimum and ascribes it to insipient precipitation. Exposure to ultraviolet has the *opposite* effect. It is further sug-

gested that the first minimum on the viscosity—time curves corresponds to the transformation, red to blue, during electrolytic coagulation. Our results, however, are not in agreement with this. In coagulations represented by Fig. 1, curves 3 and 6, visible flocculation was observed within 140 and 95 minutes respectively, the mixture remained violet for appreciably long periods within which the viscosity remained practically constant. No sensible change in the colour was observed even in later stages of the above coagulations; the viscosity—time curves, however, show a series of maxima and minima. In coagulations corresponding to Fig. 1, curves 2, 4, and 5, there was flocculation within about 1 hour; the sol had, however, changed to violet almost immediately on the addition of the electrolyte and no special colour change was noticed, corresponding to either the first or any of the subsequent minima on the viscosity—time curves. It follows, therefore, in agreement with earlier results with different colloid systems (Joshi and Jaya Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 254) that, than those dependent on merely colour or turbidity changes, the viscosity measurements might under certain conditions be more sensitive to micellar reactions, and therefore, better adapted to bring out the characteristic 'zonal' character of a *slow* coagulation.

The results of the determination of n_D the refractive index during coagulations with solutions of potassium chloride shown in Fig. 2,

FIG. 2.

fully confirm the above deduction about the 'zonal effect' constituting a *slow* coagulation. A number of observations were made

with differently concentrated solutions of sodium chloride, barium chloride and gold chloride, as also of potassium chloride of strengths other than those reported here. The principal feature of all these coagulation—time curves were completely analogous to those shown by those in Fig. 2. Curves 7a and 7b, Fig. 2, refer to n_D -time changes under conditions as identical as possible. It is seen that although the details are not reproducible, the identity of the general form in revealing the occurrence of 'zones' is definite. The results with sodium chloride showed a much greater number of 'zones', *i.e.*, the discontinuities, and that the net change in n_D , the refractive index was less than with potassium chloride. Also in agreement with results reported elsewhere on colloid manganese dioxide (*Kolloid. Z.*, 1936, 76, 145), the net diminution in the last quantity was small for every small concentrations of the coagulant. In view of the very large amount of experimental work reported in the literature on the optical properties of gold sols, both when pure and subjected to coagulation, it is not a little interesting that no observations, *earlier than these*, appear to have been made about the 'zonal' variation of n_D during coagulations in the *slow* region. As observed in similar studies of n_D variations during coagulations, the 'zonal effect' tends to disappear for very *slow* and also during rapid coagulations.

S U M M A R Y.

Changes in the viscosity and n_D , the refractive index in the Zsigmondy gold sol during coagulations by NaCl, KCl, BaCl₂ and (for n_D) AuCl₃ have been examined. In agreement with earlier findings it has been concluded that a net rise of viscosity is not necessarily a concomitant of coagulation. The two changes might be even in opposite senses. Contrary to the results of Galecki, the occurrence of minima on the viscosity—time curve is independent of the colour change, red to blue, during coagulation. The progress of viscosity change has been found to be *zonal* or discontinuous with respect to coagulation time in the *slow* region. The refractive index measurements also show this *zonal effect*: this last is most pronounced in moderately *slow* coagulations.

